

AI Transparency Statement Evaluation Instrument

Replication Package — Evaluation Rubric

Note: This instrument was developed and applied in May 2025 against Version 1.1 of the DTA Policy for Responsible Use of AI in Government (effective 1 September 2024), as part of the empirical study: **AI Transparency: Governance Compliance or Stakeholder Requirements? An Empirical Analysis of Australian Government AI Transparency Statements**. A revised Version 2.0 of the policy took effect on 15 December 2025 and introduces additional requirements. The current standard is available at: <https://www.digital.gov.au/ai/ai-in-government-policy/standard-ai-transparency-statements>

Scoring Scale

Score	Meaning
0	Not addressed — criterion is absent from the statement
1	Partially addressed — criterion is mentioned but vague, incomplete, or unclear
2	Clearly and fully addressed — criterion is explicitly and specifically met

Criteria Grouping and Stakeholder Mapping

The 20 evaluation criteria are organised into three thematic groups derived from the DTA mandate. Each group is mapped to the primary stakeholder class it serves within the RCIN framework.

20 Evaluation Criteria	Thematic Group	Primary Stakeholder Class
1A Current AI use intent 1B Future AI adoption intent 2A Usage pattern classification 2B Domain identification 3A Direct public interaction 3B Human review prior to impact	AI Use & Planning	System Implementers & Org. Deployers
4A Performance monitoring 4B Formal oversight mechanisms 5 Legal/regulatory compliance 6 Negative impact mitigation 7A DTA policy alignment 7B Australian AI ethics alignment	Governance & Risk Mgmt	Rule-setting Authorities
8 Public accessibility 9A Publication date 9B Last updated date 10 Review/update cycle 11 Plain language clarity 12 Public contact mechanism 13A Homepage discoverability 13B Navigation ease	Public Accountability & Accessibility	Affected Individuals & Citizens

AI Use & Planning (1A-3B) Governance & Risk Management (4A-7B) Public Accountability & Accessibility (8-13B)

Evaluation Criteria

Score each criterion based strictly on explicit textual disclosure in the transparency statement. Do not infer from organisational context or external knowledge.

Criterion Group	#	Evaluation Question	Description	Scoring Guide	Score (0-2)	Justification / Notes
	1A	Does the statement clearly explain why the agency is currently using AI?	Clearly articulates motivations for current AI deployment.	0 = No mention of current AI use 1 = Vague or implied use 2 = Clearly stated current use with rationale		
	1B	Does the statement clearly explain the agency's intention for future AI adoption?	Clearly outlines future plans or potential areas for AI adoption.	0 = No mention of future AI use 1 = Vague or implied intention 2 = Clearly stated future plans		
	2A	Does the statement identify the AI usage pattern according to the standard's categories?	Usage patterns include: decision-support, text generation, classification, anomaly detection, etc.	0 = No pattern identified 1 = General mention of pattern 2 = Specific pattern named and described		
AI Use & Planning	2B	Does the statement identify the domain or operational area where AI is used?	Domain examples: regulatory services, financial audits, customer support, healthcare administration.	0 = No domain identified 1 = General operational context mentioned 2 = Specific domain named		
	3A	Does the statement say whether the AI system directly interacts with the public?	Clearly states if AI directly engages with external users (e.g. chatbots, automated decisions).	0 = No mention 1 = Indirect or implied mention 2 = Clear confirmation or denial of public interaction		
	3B	Does the statement explain whether a human intermediary is involved before AI outputs affect the public?	Clarifies if human review occurs before an AI-driven decision or action impacts a person.	0 = No mention of human review 1 = Implicit or general reference 2 = Clear statement of human review process		
	4A	Does the statement describe how the agency monitors or evaluates the performance of its AI systems?	Describes methods like regular reviews, audits, validation tests, or performance dashboards.	0 = No monitoring described 1 = General mention of performance monitoring 2 = Specific monitoring methods described		
	4B	Does the statement describe formal oversight mechanisms (e.g. committees, governance boards)?	Identifies specific governance structures responsible for AI use oversight.	0 = No mention of oversight body 1 = Vague or implied oversight 2 = Named bodies or roles with responsibilities		
Governance & Risk Mgmt	5	Does the statement explain how the AI use complies with legal or regulatory requirements?	References to Privacy Act, DTA Policy, or other applicable legislation.	0 = No mention of legal compliance 1 = Generic mention of compliance 2 = Specific legislation or policy referenced		
	6	Does the statement describe efforts to assess risks and protect the public from negative AI impacts?	Explains harm analysis or risk minimisation steps taken by the agency.	0 = No risk discussion 1 = Mentions risk with no mitigation detail 2 = Identifies and describes specific mitigation measures		
	7A	Does the statement show how the agency complies with the DTA's AI Policy?	Refers directly to the Australian Government's DTA AI Policy (or equivalent).	0 = No mention of DTA Policy 1 = Implicit reference to government policy 2 = Specific DTA Policy referenced		
	7B	Does the statement demonstrate alignment with the Australian AI ethical principles?	Mentions ethical values even if DTA Policy is not cited explicitly.	0 = No ethical principles mentioned 1 = General ethical claims without specifics 2 = Named ethical principles cited		

Criterion Group	#	Evaluation Question	Description	Scoring Guide	Score (0-2)	Justification / Notes
	8	Is the statement easily accessible on the agency's public-facing website?	Clearly published online with a working public link.	0 = Not published or broken link 1 = Requires effort to find or access 2 = Freely and easily accessible		
	9A	Does the statement display when it was first published?	Shows the original public release date of the AI transparency statement.	0 = No publish date shown 1 = General timeframe only (e.g. "published last year") 2 = Specific date displayed		
	9B	Does the statement show when it was last updated?	States the last update date clearly.	0 = No update date or very old update (>2 years) 1 = Borderline update (~1.5-2 years) 2 = Updated within past year		
Public Accountability & Accessibility	10	Does the statement commit to regular reviews or updates after significant AI-related changes?	Mentions review frequency or triggers for updates.	0 = No mention of updates 1 = Implicit or outdated update process 2 = Explicit review cycle or triggers stated		
	11	Is the language understandable to the general public and free from technical jargon?	Consistent with plain English and Australian Government Style Manual.	0 = Heavy jargon or unclear language 1 = Mix of jargon and plain English 2 = Fully plain language throughout		
	12	Is a public contact method (email or link) provided for questions or feedback?	Clearly provides a contact method for public enquiries.	0 = No contact provided 1 = Contact info difficult to find or indirect 2 = Clear and direct contact method provided		
	13 A	Is the AI transparency statement linked or accessible directly from the homepage or main navigation?	Statement should be accessible within 1-2 clicks from the homepage.	0 = Buried or difficult to find 1 = Somewhat visible but requires multiple clicks 2 = Prominently linked from main navigation		
	13 B	Is it easy for a typical member of the public to navigate to the statement without prior knowledge?	Measures user-centred design and logical placement for finding the statement.	0 = Requires search to find 1 = Indirect navigation possible but non-intuitive 2 = Intuitive navigation for a general user		

Supplementary Qualitative Metrics

These metrics were not used as primary analytical outcomes but examined whether evaluators with different interpretive perspectives reached divergent assessments of the same disclosures.

Metric	Scale	Definition
Ambiguity Score	1–5	Measures how specific, understandable, and transparent the language of the statement is. 1 = Highly ambiguous; 3 = Moderate specificity; 5 = Highly specific and clear
Sentiment Tone	Open / Neutral / Defensive	Open = Transparent, welcoming feedback, proactive disclosure. Neutral = Factual and balanced without strong tone. Defensive = Minimises disclosure, uses hedging language, avoids accountability.